

m.p. 126°) and (ii) (150 mg) m.p. 280° (acetate, m.p. 150°), which were identified respectively as β -sitosterol and β -sitosterol-3 β -D-glucoside on the basis of physical properties, ¹H nmr spectral data and comparison with authentic samples.

The water-soluble fraction on acid hydrolysis gave a dark brown solid (6.0 g) which was chromatographed on a silica gel column to give a mixture of two flavonoids, which were separated by preparative tlc on silica gel-G plates to give two pure compounds: (i) (50 mg) m.p. 303–04° (acetate, m.p. 202°) and (ii) (45 mg) m.p. 310–11° (acetate, m.p. 195–96°) identified as isorhamnetin and quercetin respectively.

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Chemical Constituents of the Aerial Parts of *Sisymbrium irio*

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SISYMBRIUM irio Linn. (N.O. Cruciferae) is commonly known as jangli sarson or khubkalan¹. Aqueous and ethanolic extracts of its seeds have shown various biological activities². There are reports³⁻⁵ on chemical constituents of its leaves, pollen grains, seeds and seed oil. In view of its importance in the indigenous system of medicine, the present study was undertaken.

The aerial parts of the plant (1.5 kg) were collected during winter season from the campus of Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi, and were dried in the shade, chopped into small pieces and extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic concentrate was repeatedly extracted with petroleum ether. The petrol-insoluble residue was resolved into water-soluble and water-insoluble fractions. The quantity of water-insoluble fraction was too small to warrant further studies.

The petroleum ether concentrate (15 g) on purification by column chromatography (silica gel) gave two compounds: (i) (100 mg) m.p. 137° (acetate,